

CLINICAL FEATURES OF THE COURSE OF EXUDATIVE OTITIS MEDIA IN BENIGN NEOPLASMS OF THE NOSE, PARANASAL SINUSES AND NASOPHARYNX

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Relevance. Over the past decades, the authors have noted an increase in the incidence of exudative otitis media (EOM), and it is 15-17% among all ear diseases. It is known from the scientific literature that in patients with EOM, attention should be paid to the state of the pharyngeal mouth of the auditory tubes and anatomical structures bordering on this area, since it is their pathological changes that most often lead to the development of the disease. Obstructive dysfunction is the most common cause of EOM. It can be caused by a mechanical violation of the patency of the auditory tube due to benign and malignant neoplasms of the nose, paranasal sinuses and nasopharynx.

The purpose of our study was to study the features of the clinical course of exudative otitis media in benign neoplasms of the nose, paranasal sinuses and nasopharynx.

Research materials: We conducted a retrospective analysis of the medical histories of 164 patients with benign neoplasms of the nose (DNN), paranasal sinuses (PS) and nasopharynx (NP) and 140 patients with inflammatory diseases of the nose, PS, treated in the ENT department 1 of the SamMI clinic. We conducted the following research methods: clinical, ENT examination of organs, audiological.

Results of research: According to the results of the distribution of patients by age categories (1-diagram): in the main group, the largest number of patients was found in the age group of 15-24 years, 51.2%, and 25-34 years, 25.6%, while in the control group, younger patients aged 6-14 years prevailed, 47.8%. Both in the main group and in the control group, male patients prevailed. In the main group, 74%, and in the control group, a slight predominance of 55% (2-diagram). The largest number of patients of both groups complained of difficulty in nasal breathing in the main group of 162 patients, which was 98.8%, in the control group of 136 (97.1%). It should be noted that in the main group, 122 (74.4%) complained about the unilateral process, while in the control group it was noted equally as unilateral (53%) so

is the two-way (47%) process. In the main group, the second most common symptom was a sensation of a foreign body 93.9%, while in the control group, the second most common symptom was nasal discharge of a purulent and mucous nature 97.8%. In the main group, frequent nosebleeds were also noted in 39%. Among the otological symptoms, ear congestion and hearing impairment prevailed, and patients of the main group noted them more often than the control group. We also evaluated the data on the patency of the auditory tube: in the main group, the largest number of patients accounted for 3 16.5% and 4 18.3% of the degree of patency of the auditory tube, and in the control 2 18.6% and 3 11.4% degree.

Conclusions: Our studies have shown that exudative otitis media occurs in the early stages of DON, ONP and NG, which is clinically manifested by ear congestion (51.2%), hearing impairment (45.7%), tinnitus (40.9%), a feeling of transfusionfluid in the ear (20.7%). EOM in DNN, PS and NP are characterized by a unilateral violation of the functional state of the ear (69.3%), a violation of the ventilation function of the auditory tube of the III (28.7%) and IV (31.9%) stages, conductive type of hearing loss I (61.9%), II (33.3%) stages, and there is also I (42.4%) and II (51.5%) stages of mixed type of hearing loss, a tympanogram of type B was registered in 56.2% of cases.